

Molding Graduates' Employability Traits through Relevant Academic and Training Skills

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Abstract:- The researchers used the unified/institutional checklist questionnaire, which applies to all the colleges in the institution, to conduct a tracer study. This descriptive survey research is the first institutional tracer study of the school. Every college of the institution had done their respective share of conducting a tracer study but they have their set of questions to ask from their graduates. Through the unified survey questionnaire, the 912 respondents across the Colleges were able to give relevant information based on uniform questions. As a result of the study, the researchers found that the respondents' main reason in choosing their present profession is that it is aligned with their degree programs. The respondents' academic program through their professional courses had helped them grasp the needed knowledge in their degree. Co-Curricular activities were big help in bringing out the full potential of the respondents, and it is part of their training/skills-enhancement in human relations. However, facilities were not fully maximized in helping the respondents during their school days. During their pre-employment stage, limited quota of the number of employees to be accepted in the job; and the failure in passing the job-prescribed examination were the topmost problems experienced by the respondents in their application for their first job. The respondents rated very satisfactory the quality of education offered by the institution. The researchers formulated an employability action plan to help the graduating students develop their employability traits, to get a job that matches their taken degree program the soonest possible time upon graduation.

Keywords:- Employability, Traits, Academic Skills, Training Skills, Graduates, Employability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The upliftment of the economic status of a person is associated with education. Benjamin Franklin said that *“Education is an investment in knowledge that always pays the best interest”*. The relevance of education was also emphasized by Henry Peter Brougham, who said that *“Education makes people easy to govern but impossible to enslave”*.

Part of promoting a higher education institution (HEI) is the employability of its graduates, and the relevance of the programs that they offer to address the need of the various

industries in the local and global labor market. Ripmeester (2021) mentioned in her article that based on the 2020 QS International Student Survey, a University's good ranking among the other higher education institutions is based on graduate employment (72%).

It is therefore a challenge for HEIs to focus on the employability of their graduates. As emphasized by the Employers in Malaysia, the greater emphasis on hiring is on the soft skills as opposed to hard skills. As described by the British Council, soft skills include language (English) and communication skills. It should be noted that these described skills are achievable through relevant academic and training skills.

The determination of efficacy of educational processes (instructional, management, policy), in the development of quality human capital is a priority research area on the issue of education. According to the UN Secretary General's Policy as cited by UNESCO (2020), even before the COVID-19 pandemic, 26.7 million young people were not employed. While skills in the field of data analytics, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence are in demand in the labor market around the world, education and training systems lack the capacities to prepare their graduates.

In this context, the current study determines how a higher education institution can prepare its graduates to have the traits and skills needed for their prospective job by preparing them with relevant academic and training skills. True to its mission and as a springboard in preparing its graduates, this institution envisions to produce graduates fully-equipped with knowledge, proper attitudes, values and skills. The efficacy of its services can be best assessed through its graduates in this tracer study.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Employability is all the more diversified in the 21st century. How can schools now develop strategies to fit into the jobs which require 21st century skills and learning? Who are the best people to evaluate the school's performance? Unless higher education institutions track their graduates, they have relatively little chance of assessing the real impact of study programs, academic and training skills, and their relevance to the labor market.

The concept of employability as described by UNESCO (2012), is a wide range of attributes and competencies, which serve as weapon, and advantage of a job seeker to gain and maintain employment. It includes soft and hard skills. These skills are oftentimes described as part of the 21st century skills such as, but not limited to: communication skills; logical, analytical and problem-solving skills; personality, confidence and integrity; flexibility and adaptability; innovation and creativity; and team spirit.

➤ *Bridging the Gap*

Higher education institutions prepare students for their future employment through their teaching training and the totality of the services that they offer. Academic qualifications are essentials, however, the attitudes and behaviors of graduates are equally important. The ++ plus factors which include motivation and ability to think “*outside the box*” are equally important. Higher education institutions can only do much to their graduates – prepare them academically, and guide them with proper attitude. The bottom line of employability depends on how they cooperate in the preparation of their careers and their readiness to meet the challenges of job-hunting.

Graduate’s task to evaluate a possible career path, as explained by Smurthwaite (2022) is by knowing what one is interested in; later compare it with his skills and academic preparation and strengths. What extent then should a higher education institution do to prepare its graduates to establish their employability? How do graduates address the challenge of possessing the employability traits after higher education institutions have prepared them for their careers?

➤ *Choosing the Present Profession*

Change is inevitable. Graduates prepared themselves for four years or so in their degree program but as Garrett (2018) rationalized, people go through changes. Young people are idealistic, aggressive innovative and adaptive. They explore what the modern labor market offers, at sometime, they may put their traditional field of study aside to pursue knowledge better suited to the world.

The Commission on Higher Education in the Philippines at one point set a moratorium for some degree programs, which was reported by DOLE (2010) as contributing to the oversupply of graduates. It was a decisive action on the part of CHED at that time then to encourage freshmen to opt for degree programs that offer the best chances of employment after graduation. Moreover, the mismatch challenge in the labor market with degree programs with oversupply of graduates would be minimized. Market intelligence, responsive training and education programs, adequate investments on education and training and better quality learning will pave way towards better matching of the skills of the graduates with the requirements in the job market.

Higher Education Institution like this Institution have to prepare the employability traits of their graduates for both soft and hard skills and to prepare them to the job-seeking battlefield. Academic preparation and graduates’ proper attitude and aptitude go a long way to land in a matched job where they can develop passion of.

➤ *Role of Quality Education in the Employability of Graduates.*

Higher Education Institutions are not spared in the globalization and transformation factors that are taking place. UNESCO (2018) attributes the growing graduate unemployment as major policy concern about the employability of their graduates. For HEIs to guard the employability of their graduates, Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) is adopted to help in bridging the gap between the quality of education and the employability of graduates. A modern way of defining employability requires not only the skills sets needed to enter the job market, but also the development of a broader knowledge-based that will prepare graduates to be flexible, and can apply across different employment fields the knowledge and skills they gained.

Kazakhstani Universities, as found in the study of Nugmanova (2019), believe that the quality of higher education and training of highly qualified and employable graduates are highly contributory to a sustainable and economic development of a society.

Quality of education served to students play a major role in the employability of graduates. Part of the quality of education is the facilities being utilized in the schools. It was interesting to note however that according to Boateng, et.al (2015), that inspite of the weaknesses observed by students in Wisconsin International University College, in Accra, Ghana, graduates are still very confident that the quality of training, teaching and learning, and the programs offered by the College had adequity prepared them in their jobs.

Ortiga (2018), described the state of being employable as one in which a graduate must accumulate “human capital” through higher education, with the assumption that more education represents a higher level of skill. The development of the Philippines’ labor-brokering strategies came with the emergence of higher education system, which prepare graduates to be employable abroad. Scholars have attributed the overseas success of Filipino nurses, for example, to the higher education institutions, which offer curriculum in consonance with the needs of foreign employers.

The current study aimed to identify the level of quality of learning that this institution offers, that could help its graduates develop their employability traits.

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The employability of graduates is part of the responsibility of higher education institutions. But it is also believed that graduates need to be responsible themselves for the great job. Their personal accountability weighs more than any career path advice anybody can give. Academic mentors religiously provide the needed knowledge and skills to the students to forge a better employability trait. But an assessment as to how these knowledge and skills provided need to be known from the graduates themselves to help in the continuous quest of better education on the part of the higher education institutions.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

- To determine the main reason in choosing the graduates’ present profession/job.
- To rate the quality of education that this institution offers through its academic programs.
- To determine how the graduates are being helped in their employment through the academic programs and skills trainings.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The present study employs descriptive research with the use of survey questionnaire as data-collection tool to randomly selected graduates of the following programs: Bachelor of Secondary Education, Bachelor of Science in Criminology, Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management, Bachelor of Science in Computer Studies, Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering, Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration, and Bachelor of Science in Accountancy.

A. Main Reasons in Choosing the Graduates Present Profession (Summary)

Matching the right person to the right job indeed gives benefits to both the applicant and the company. A company can tap the strengths of the person to assign him to a job that will make use of his strengths. A company as a result of the match, as described by People Dynamics (2021), can build the person’s self-esteem and help increase his job performance.

Table 1. Reasons for Choosing the Profession

Main Reason	Frequency (f)	Percentage (P)	Ranking (R)
1. Present Profession is aligned with the degree program taken	389	33	1
2. It is the only job available during the application	118	10	4
3. It interests and gives satisfaction to the graduates	352	30	2
4. It directs the graduate to his mission in life to serve	214	18	3
5. Friends/Relatives influences the graduate to be in the present profession	73	6	6
6. It gives the graduate a chance to divert to different profession	36	3	6
7. Others, if applicable	0	0	7
Total		100%	

It is evident that in Table 1, more of the graduates, coming from various disciplines have job match in their present profession. The 33% are graduates that characterize their present profession is aligned with their degree programs taken. It is close to the 30% that the graduates’ present profession interests in and gives them satisfaction.

Going for the job one loves goes a long way. When one gets to use his strengths in his job everyday as posited by Batiman (2022), he tends to be more confident; more likely to achieve his goals; he is more effective at growing and developing himself; he is more engaged in his work; and he experiences lesser stress. Seemingly, most of the graduates have the interests in their hearts; the interests would help them establish their job satisfaction in their present profession. Doing an aligned job that matches one’s degree program is a great job. When one do a great job, he becomes more confident.

There are options that can be done when one’s degree does not match his career plans. Delaney (2023) believes that when one’s career does not quite fit with what he chose to

study, there are always skills learned that are learned in the degree that can be transferred to another. If not too far along with his degree, the way to recalibrate it is to simply change course. Doing this however requires a concrete and proper frame of mind so that one can develop interest and passion in his newly-discovered profession. Reflections, advices from credible persons and prayers are necessary to re-direct his thoughts.

Having matched-job or unmatched job requires being creative, innovative and passionate to do the assigned tasks. There are circumstances when an employee has matched job but quits from the job because of internal and external factors. Unmatched job which consequently gives an employee a poor job fit can be a cause of disengagement, however, it can also be a challenge to conquer and to discover what good is in store for him.

B. Factors being considered in determining the quality of Education

Quality of education had been defined differently by different experts. The seventeen (17) sustainable development

goals (SDG) of UNESCO had included Quality of Education (SDG No. 4) – as crucial in the attainment of the other SDGs. Quality education specifically entails issues such as

appropriate skills development; teacher factors in education like materials and resources; and infrastructure and facilities.

Table 2. Quality of Education Offered (through the Academic Factors) Summary

Academic Factors	E (5)	VS (4)	S (3)	SS (2)	NS (1)	AWM	DC
1. Appropriate Professional/Major Courses	23 (115)	825 (3,300)	86 (258)	1 (2)	0 (0)	3.90	VS
2. Relevant General Education Courses	12 (60)	770 (3,080)	84 (252)	86 (3,392)	0 (0)	3.92	VS
3. Textbooks required by the teachers	22 (110)	477 (1,908)	93 (279)	592 (2187)	0 (0)	3.69	VS
4. Updated Reference Books utilized for the course	51 (255)	246 (984)	64 (192)	361 (7,431)	0 (0)	4.96	E
5. Use of instructional materials such as study guide, manuals, work books, handbooks	14 (70)	781 (3,124)	99 (297)	3 (6)	0 (0)	3.90	VS
6. Use of practicum/hands-on instruction	30 (150)	707 (2,828)	69 (207)	5 (10)	0 (0)	3.94	VS
7. Substantial Academic Preparation of Teachers	20 (100)	760 (3,040)	11 (333)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.90	VS
8. Appropriate Teaching Techniques and styles used by teachers	15 (75)	724 (2,896)	56 (168)	795 (3,139)	0 (0)	3.95	VS
9. Conditioning the readiness of the students in their lessons	19 (95)	737 (2,948)	39 (117)	7 (14)	0 (0)	3.95	VS
10. Curriculum is relevant to the job	17 (85)	753 (3,012)	39 (117)	7 (14)	0 (0)	3.96	VS
11. Others, if applicable	0	0	0	0	0		
General Weighted Mean						3.64	VS

Legend: E – Excellent, VS – Very Satisfactory, S – Satisfactory, SS – Slightly Satisfactory, NS – Not Satisfactory

Likert Scale:

SCALE	SCALE LIMIT	EQUIVALENT	DESCRIPTIVE CODE
5	4.20-5.00	Excellent	E
4	3.20-4.19	Very Satisfactory	VS
3	2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	S
2	1.80-2.59	Slightly Satisfactory	SS
1	1.00-1.75	Not Satisfactory	NS

Table 2 evidently shows that in general, the quality of education, with the identified indicators is very satisfactory. Updated reference books utilized for the course is noted to be excellent (4.96).

Preparing graduates to be employable is anchored on the quality of education that help them develop sustainable livelihoods. This institution prepares its graduates to be economically- productive through the academic factors identified. Graduates are not only to be prepared to meet the minimum standard of academic learning, but even to target beyond the minimum. Education is evolving, and this institution addresses the educational dynamics through its various activities. UNESCO described textbooks as the most visible aspects of curriculum and are considered as main scripts that shape the teaching and learning processes. It is also

to be noted that this institution offers relevant curriculum. While there are guidelines in the formulation of curriculum, this institution has designed its curricula, taking into consideration the needs of students, particularly in their electives and general education courses. Professional courses are mandated by the Commission on Higher Education Memorandum (CHED Memo) of their respective programs. Curriculum as defined by Rowntree (1981) and Priestley (2019), refers to the total structure of learning areas and activities developed by an educational institution to meet the learning needs of students, and to achieve desired educational aims. The learning experiences of students therefore revolves through the curriculum. Its implementation is dependent on how creative, innovative and passionate the teachers are in the delivery of their teaching piece.

Quality of Education as found by Verspoor (1989) requires educational reforms in the areas of administrative development; teacher training, and strategies to gain the commitment of implementors, external agencies, and government authorities. It can be deduced that to improve quality education to prepare graduates for their employability does not require only a relevant curriculum or relevant learning materials. The commitment of the implementors to help in the realization of the goals for quality education is also a major impact to consider.

➤ *Institutional Help through the Academic Programs*

Solid system of education as stated in the research of Tuzlukova, et.al (2019), is the collegiate experience, which addresses the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values characteristics of educated persons. Such type of experience is described as general education. These experiences on various areas are facilitated by teachers, and enhanced by relevant curriculum and learning materials.

Table 3. Ways in which Graduates are helped by the Institution through Academic Programs (Summary)

WAYS	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Ranking (R)
1. Academic/Professional Courses help the graduates to grasp the needed knowledge in his degree	735	18	1
2. General education courses have molded his values in his work	445	11	6
3. Textbooks and Learning materials available are relevant in his studies	378	9	7
4. Teachers strategically position their teaching based on the needs of their students	671	16	3
5. Teachers are hands on in the teaching-learning process	661	15	4
6. Teachers are academically prepared in teaching their courses	718	17	2
7. Curriculum addresses the competencies needed	592	14	5
8. Others, if applicable	0	100%	8

It is evident in Table 3 that academics/professional courses being offered by this institution helped the graduates to grasp the needed knowledge in their respective degree programs. Teachers who are academically prepared in teaching the various courses were also of great help to the graduates.

Graduates relied on the academic/professional courses as the primary sources of knowledge that they grasped while in this school. This finding implies that this institution has invested on the professional development of its teachers to achieve their full potential to effectively teach about their field of expertise. Professional courses are the foundation of the graduates to appreciate more their field of specialization, and for them to have a deeper commitment in their field so that they can develop passion in it. To prepare the teachers academically, this institution conducts a periodic faculty development seminars and workshops: They are also being evaluated in terms of their teaching performance. They are also encouraged to engage in research and community involvement activities.

Investing in learning brings many benefits to both personal and professional life, according to SBB (2022). Application of what has been learned in school to the job is essential to retain knowledge and skills, and which can be carried all throughout the employment life. Teachers teaching the academic/professional courses have experiences, oftentimes in their respective field or industry. The richness of their experiences that they can impart to their students are important to help the latter in their jobs when they will work. Teachers, as opined by Wilichowski, et.al (2021) are the single most important school-based determinant and important role in developing students knowledge, skills and values.

➤ *Institutional Help through Training Skills*

Life skills are important in navigating relationships and in making day-to-day decisions in the workplace and even outside the workplace. Work-life balance skills can be partly learned through various activities in school like extra-curricular and co-curricular activities.

Table 4. Ways in which Graduates are helped through Training

Ways of Training Skills	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Ranking (R)
1. Co-curricular activities are maximized to bring out full potentials of the graduates	808	26	1
2. Facilities are provided to aid the graduates in their skills	437	14	5
3. Enhancement of Skills (soft and hard skills) is done through in-house or outside seminars and activities	724	23	2
4. Actual conduct of research to appreciate the field more	632	21	3
5. Community involvement is an important venue for social awareness	492	16	4
6. Others, if applicable	0	0	6

Total		100%	
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Co-curricular activities as stated by Sarkar (2022) are those, which are carried out outside the normal classrooms, and they supplement the academic curriculum. Skills developed in these activities are problem-solving, reasoning, critical thinking, communication and collaborative abilities. Table 4 shows that co-curricular activities are maximized to bring out the full potentials of the graduates. It implies that teachers in this institution are not confined with mere lectures or learnings inside the classroom. Students are also brought out from the institution like company /hotel familiarization, or even field trips to learn more about their future profession. Enhancement of skills (soft and hard skills) is done through in-house or outside seminars and activities. Since the instructional guides of the institution require course outcome assessment of every student, which is before the end of the semester, outcome-based activities in every course is required. Soft skills and hard skills are sets of skills that make graduates effective team members in the workplace.

Daniyal, et.al (2012), mentioned in her research that spending more time in co-curricular activities (formal activities) like sports, debate, music and dramatic activities helps one in getting high grade, but those spending more time in leisure gets poorer academic performance. In the research of Leung, et.al (2011) however, it was found that participation in

co-curricular activities could not enhance student learning effectiveness. In the current study, the finding of Daniyal, et.al (2012) is affirmed. The graduates of this institution acknowledged the fact that engaging in co-curricular activities are maximized to bring out their full potentials. Such potentials may include their ability to develop their human relations skills through their interaction with other members of the group; to foster artistic creativity and problem-solving in students; and to pinpoint weaknesses in students that can immediately be addressed. These potentials which are developed in the school can serve as tools for graduates to apply in their works.

In both instances, co-curricular activities and the enhancement of the soft skills and hard skills of the graduates help them in their present profession. These traits are basic for the graduates to utilize in their work dealings.

➤ *Getting Employed: The Problems*

Job-hunting can be an exhaustive task. The longer the hunting, it is more likely that a job applicant feels less confident and loses momentum. Motivation drive is weakened, but there is a need to keep the spirit of job-seeking burning because he is also eager to get employed.

Table 5. Problems Encountered in Getting Employed (Summary)

	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Ranking (R)
1. Limited quota during the application period	613	24	1
2. Failure to pass the prescribed examination	518	20	2
3. Health-related problems	76	3	7.5
4. Failure to complete the documentary requirements during the application period	510	19	3
5. Lacks required eligibility on the job being applied for	247	9	5
6. Insufficient fund to cover the cost of job application	131	5	6
7. Lacks work experience/s needed for the job being applied	391	15	4
8. Distance of the workplace/job area is far from residence	80	3	7.5
9. Low salary	41	2	9
10. Others, if applicable			
Total		100%	

Table 5 clearly identified the primary problems of the graduates in job-hunting. There are some companies, which set quota during the application period; and the graduates may also fail to pass the prescribed examination. Close to the second reason is the failure to complete the documentary requirements during the application period.

The results as shown in Table 5 may imply that the foremost reason which is the limited quota during the application period is somehow uncontrollable by the applicants. Companies may sometimes set limit to applicant pool. Companies may find sorting of application papers time-

consuming, although large number of applicant pool can be streamlined by conducting pre-employment tests. Graduates may find problems on the submission of needed or required documents, which may have been caused by delay. Pre-employment test results maybe used to narrow down large applicant pools. Failing in the prescribed examination among the graduates may show lack of preparation or they may not be qualified in the job that they are applying, since the job applied for requires different field of specialization.

Setting quota in hiring maybe in terms of number, gender, culture or other diversity factors. In number, some

companies or educational institution for that matter opt to limit the number of applicants, through first come first served basis. In gender, diversity of people who work in an organization maybe limited to specific gender. But there are already female working in the male’s world and vice versa. Setting a gender limit may become discriminatory. OECD (2015) describes gender inequality as one of the most primitive and oldest forms of inequality. However, HR Asia (2022) opined that setting targets or quotas to hire a more diverse crew can be an opportunity to focus on finding diverse, new talent who can bring new value to the organization. The bulk of applicants may not be necessary as earlier applicants may have satisfied the required qualifications and even more for a particular position. This instance limits the decision-making period on the part of the Human Resource Manager.

The current study is inclined to help this institution’s graduates to beat the quota requirement through proper planning and preparation. Oftentimes, pre-employment assessment is composed of the basic knowledge about general IQ, and basic knowledge about the organization and the industry where it belongs.

➤ *Employability Action Plan*

Creating an action plan that drives results in necessary to improve a particular situation, and to achieve its goals. The results of the current study gave the researchers the opportunity to develop an employability action plan that may help the graduates attain their goals of landing a job. The indicators were taken from the areas of the results (from the tables presented) that necessarily requires attention.

Table 6 Employability Action Plan (Proposal)

Areas of Concern	Result based on the Current Research	Target Objectives	Strategy	People Involved	Expected Output
A. Quality of Education (as perceived by Graduates) >Textbooks required by teachers	The Library has updated book references however graduates perceived that the textbooks required by teachers are inappropriate in preparing for their employment.	To provide students with updated book/ Material references aligned with their degree programs and which help them develop employability traits.	(1) Teachers need to properly evaluate books being offered by publishing companies before recommending its purchased (2) Choosing of books which integrate values and skills enhancement at work.	>Chief Librarian >Publishing Companies >Teachers	Appropriate textbooks for the courses. It contributes to: (1) enhancement of life long learning. (2) retention of knowledge.
B. Institutional Help 1. Academic Programs >Textbooks and learning materials relevant to their studies	Most of the graduates respondents perceived that the textbooks and learning materials do not prepare them for employment	To provide students with updated book/ Material references aligned with their degree programs and which help them develop employability traits.	Choosing of books which integrate values and skills enhancement at work.	>Chief Librarian >Publishing Companies >Teachers	Appropriate textbooks to enhance life-long learning skills.
2. General Education courses help in the molding of values needed in the work	Graduates – Respondents perceive that general education courses are not maximized to help them mold their values for work.	To maximize the benefits of general education courses	(1) Graduates to read inspirational books that could boost their confidence in the workplace. (2) General Education Teachers to provide activities that forge application of values needed in the work.	>Students >Teachers	Confident graduates ready for work.
3. Training Skills >Facilities are provided to aid the graduates in their skills	Graduates are provided with the standard facilities required by CHED or other accrediting body, however,	To maximize the benefits of standard facilities	(1) Part of the outcome-based activities is to utilize the facilities provided by the institution (2) Periodic assessment	>Teachers >Students	Well-versed graduates, adoptable to the utilization of facilities

	these are not maximized		shall be conducted to determine whether students have immersed themselves in gaining skills with the facilities		
<p>C. Problems encountered in looking for employment</p> <p>a) Limited Quota in the number of allowed applicants</p> <p>b. Failure to pass the prescribed examination</p>	<p>>Graduates can not oftentimes be part of the quota for the applicants pool</p> <p>>Basic Examination requirement is part of the hiring process</p>	To produce graduates who are ready for employment	<p>(1) Facilitate the application of graduates by streamlining the procedures in the issuance of credentials</p> <p>(2) Career Guidance</p>	>Graduates >Proper Offices	Graduates to be part of the Applicants' Pool and to be employed in the job that matches their degree program.

IV. CONCLUSION

Preparing graduates for employment is a big task. Higher education institution do not have only the responsibility of molding their graduates with the best knowledge, skills and values, but to ensure them that they have the employability traits needed in their future profession. While the skills, knowledge, and experience the graduates need to find employment are evolving, they also shall shoulder the responsibility of enhancing their capabilities to meet the demands of the labor market. Nowadays, life-long learnings are important to survive in dealing diversities in the workplace. Employers are seeking graduates as Proctera (2022) believes somebody who can think critically, solve problems creatively, develop innovative strategies, and communicate with confidence. The best weapons to employability are preparation and readiness.

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